

IMPROVING STUDENT LEARNING OUTCOMES USING AUDIO VISUAL MEDIA ON PLANT PARTS AND THEIR FUNCTIONS TOPIC AT CLASS 4 SD NEGERI 1 PAGAR ALAM OF PAGAR ALAM CITY**Anggela Nanda Rahma Saputra**

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Abstract: Learning in the digital era demands innovative and interactive approaches to increase student interest and understanding. This research aims to measure the effectiveness of using audio-visual media in improving the learning outcomes of class IV students at SD Negeri 1 Pagar Alam on plant parts and their functions. Using a collaborative classroom action research (PTK) method consisting of two cycles, this research involved 22 students. Data obtained from observations and learning evaluations. In the pre-cycle, only 22.73% of students reached the KKM. After applying image media in cycle I, the percentage increased to 54.55%. The use of audio visual media in cycle II showed a significant increase, with 86.36% of students reaching or exceeding the KKM. These results indicate that audio visual media is effective in improving student learning outcomes. Apart from that, this media is able to make learning more interesting, increase engagement, and facilitate students' understanding of scientific concepts. This research provides practical benefits for students and teachers, especially in creating a more dynamic and relevant learning environment in the digital era

Keywords: Digital Learning, Audio Visual Media, Learning Outcomes.

This is an open-access article under the [CC-BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) license**Introduction**

Education is not only the responsibility of parents, educational institutions or the government, but is a collective responsibility. strategies and the role of teachers as the most important part of an educational institution, which does not just transfer knowledge, so teachers are required to be able to choose various options. appropriate learning strategies and the role of a competent teacher, so that the goal of improving the quality of student learning can be achieved (Azmi, 2022). Learning in the digital era demands a more innovative and interactive approach in order to attract students' interest and increase understanding. At SD Negeri 1 Pagar Alam, this challenge is felt, especially in learning about plants and their functions in class 4. Classical methods such as lectures and the use of textbooks are often less effective in conveying material that is still conceptual in nature. This of course makes students behave passively and are less involved in the learning process.

After conducting observations at SDN 1 Pagar ALam, it was found that the majority of students showed a decreasing interest in natural science (IPA). Conditions like this certainly result in low academic achievement and understanding of very important scientific concepts. In the Big Indonesian Dictionary (2018), "Achievement is a result that has been achieved (from what has been done, done, etc.)". Meanwhile, according to Witherington (2003), achievement is a result achieved by an individual through effort that is experienced directly and is a skill activity in a certain situation. The word science itself comes from the word science which means nature. Meanwhile, according to Suyoso (1998: 23), science is "knowledge resulting from human activity which is active and dynamic incessantly and is obtained through certain, systematic, objective, methodical and universally applicable methods". Abdullah (1998: 18), believes that science is "theoretical knowledge that is obtained or compiled in a unique or special way , namely by observing, experimenting, inferring, constructing theories, experimentation, observation and so on by linking one method to another. another way".

Based on the opinions expressed by the experts above, it can be concluded that Natural Sciences (IPA) is knowledge from the results of human activities obtained by using scientific steps. Therefore, to make science learning more interesting for elementary school students, a technology-based learning approach is needed so that a more interesting and dynamic learning environment can be created. Choosing the right and effective media will of course determine the success or failure of the learning carried out

This research aims to measure the extent to which audio visual media can improve the learning outcomes of class IV students at SD Negeri 1 Pagar Alam in material about plants and their functions. This research also aims to improve learning that has been carried out by previous researchers, with the hope of increasing students' interest and understanding of science material.

Through a holistic and integrated approach, it is hoped that we can create an interesting, motivating and relevant learning environment for students in this digital era. Specifically, this research will answer the following questions, 1). Can audio-visual media improve the learning outcomes of class IV students at SD Negeri 1 Pagar Alam? and 2). How do the learning outcomes of class IV students at SD Negeri 1 Kota Pagar Alam improve after using audio-visual media?

From the results of this research, it is hoped that it can provide practical benefits for all parties involved in the world of education, especially for all students and teachers at SD Negeri 1 Pagar Alam. For students, it is hoped that this research can contribute to providing a new and more interesting learning experience, so that they become more enthusiastic and active during learning. For teachers, this research can be used as a reference in implementing more effective and interesting science learning, in accordance with technological developments and the characteristics of modern students.

Methods

Research with the title "Improving Student Learning Outcomes Using Audio Visual Media Material on Plant Parts and Their Functions in Class 4 of SD Negeri 1 Pagar Alam Of Pagar Alam City" using a collaborative Class Action Research (PTK) design consisting of two cycles and

implementation through four stages, namely the planning stage, implementation stage, observation stage, and reflection.

This research was carried out at SD Negeri 1 Pagaram City, which consisted of 2 cycles . Cycle I was carried out on Monday 1 May 2024, and cycle II was carried out on Monday 11 May 2024. The subjects in this research were 22 class IV students at SD Negeri 1 Pagaram City. The data produced in this learning improvement is in the form of supervisors' observations of teacher activities in teaching and student learning outcomes in recognizing plant parts and their functions.

During the pre-cycle implementation, the author provides material about plant parts and their functions, based on the evaluation results. Unsatisfactory results were obtained, namely 77.27% of students got scores below the KKM, and 22.73% of students were able to get scores beyond the KKM. That means there are only 5 students out of 22 whose scores are above the KKM.

In implementing cycle 1, the author designed learning by preparing lesson plans and starting to use image media. From the evaluation carried out, an increase in learning outcomes was obtained, namely 54.55% of students were able to reach the KKM and the remaining 45.45% of students still had not reached the KKM. The author continues the implementation of learning improvements by holding cycle II. This was done because improvements in cycle 1, although there had been improvements, were not yet in line with the target expected by the author, namely 75% of students had to reach the KKM (obtain a score above 70).

In implementing cycle II, the author revised the lesson plans according to the results of cycle 1 reflection and changed the media to audio-visual media so that it was easier for students to understand the material. After explaining the material using audio-visual media, the author gave a test or evaluation to class IV D students. The results obtained turned out that student learning outcomes had increased more significantly compared to learning outcomes in cycle 1, there were 86.36% of students whose grades had reached even beyond KKM. This is in accordance with the target of learning completeness, namely learning is said to be complete if students get a score of 70. From the percentage above it can be seen that there has been a change in student learning outcomes which shows an increase in students achieving the KKM from cycle I to cycle II. In the pre-cycle the number of students who had not completed was 17 people, after the first cycle there were only 10 people left, and in the second cycle there were only 3 students who had not yet completed it with a percentage of only 13.63%.

Results and Discussion

During the pre-cycle implementation, the author provides material regarding plant parts and their functions to students. Evaluation is carried out to measure how far students understand the material that has been presented. The results of the evaluation show that the majority of students have not reached an adequate level of understanding. To be precise, 77.27 % of students scored below the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM), which indicates that the majority of students have not succeeded in understanding the material well. Only 22.73 % of students were able to get a score above the KKM, or in other words, only 5 out of 22 students managed to achieve a satisfactory score.

Untung Trisna Suwaji, M.Si, (2016:2) states that learning completeness is the minimum level of achieving competency in attitudes, knowledge and skills which includes complete mastery of the substance and completeness of learning in the context of the learning period. Furthermore, complete mastery of the substance is the completeness of students' learning for each basic competency (KD) determined

In implementing cycle 1, the author evaluated learning by preparing a more structured RPP (Learning Implementation Plan) and starting to use image media to convey material regarding plant parts and their functions. This step was taken as an effort to improve students' understanding after unsatisfactory results in the pre-cycle.

Hamzah Pagarra (2022) said that learning media can clarify the presentation of messages and information so that it can make classroom learning run smoothly and improve learning processes and outcomes. The use of image media aims to make the material more interesting and easy for students to understand. Image media can help students to better visualize abstract concepts, so that they can relate theory to the real images they see.

From the evaluation carried out after the application of image media in cycle 1, there was a significant increase in student learning outcomes. A total of 54.55 % of students succeeded in reaching the KKM, which shows an increase in understanding compared to pre-cycle. This increase is an indication that the use of image media has a positive impact on student understanding. However, 45.45 % of students still have not reached the KKM, which means that almost half of the students still need further help to understand the material well.

In the implementation of cycle II, the author made improvements to the RPP (Learning Implementation Plan) based on the results of reflection from cycle I. In addition, the learning media used was also changed from image media to audio-visual media. This change was made with the aim of making it easier for students to understand material about plant parts and their functions. Audio-visual media was chosen because it has the potential to increase student engagement and facilitate understanding through a combination of visual and audio elements.

Hamzah Pagarra (2022) Audio visual learning media is learning media that presents audio and visual elements simultaneously so that students get messages or information from visualizations in the form of words or images accompanied by sound. The sound can be in the form of a visual explanation displayed, dialogue or just a sound effect such as music. The presence of audio elements allows students to receive learning messages through hearing, while the visual elements make it possible to create learning messages through visualization.

After explaining the material using audio visual media, the author gave a test or evaluation to class IV D students. The evaluation results showed a significant increase in student learning outcomes compared to cycle I. In cycle II, as many as 86.36% of students succeeded in reaching or exceeding the KKM (Minimum Completeness Criteria). This indicates that almost all students have understood the material well, in accordance with the learning completion targets set, namely students are considered complete if they get a score of 70 or more.

The significant increase in learning outcomes from cycle I to cycle II can be seen from the change in the number of students who reach the KKM. In the pre-cycle, only 5 out of 22 students (22.73 %) achieved the KKM, while in the first cycle this number increased to 12 out of 22 students (54.55%). However, there are still 10 students (45.45%) who have not reached the KKM in cycle I. Through improvements made in cycle II, the number of students who have not yet completed it has been reduced drastically to only 3 people (13.64%), while 19 out of 22 students (86.36%) have reached or exceeded the KKM.

From the percentage above, it is clear that the improvements made in cycle II succeeded in improving student learning outcomes significantly. In the pre-cycle, there were 17 students who had not finished. After the implementation of cycle I, the number of students who had not yet completed was reduced to 10 students, and in cycle II, only 3 students remained who had not reached the KKM. This shows that changing learning strategies using audio-visual media has had a large positive impact on students' understanding.

One expert in the field of education believes that media is a tool that has the function of conveying messages (Sari et al., 2019 in Bovee, 1997). We can interpret the term media as various things that can act as intermediaries or transmitters of information from someone who is the sender of the message to another person who is the recipient of the message. John D. Latuheru stated that the media has an educational function, namely that the media provides information that contains educational values.

Audio-visual learning media is one potential solution to overcome this problem. As said by Wina Sanjaya (2014: 118), audio visual media is a type of media that not only contains sound elements but also contains image elements that can be seen, for example video recordings , sound slides, various sizes of film and so on... In line with this opinion. Yudhi Munadi (2008:55) believes that the media Audio visual is a medium that involves the senses of hearing and sight at the same time in one process. The nature of the messages that can be transmitted are in the form of verbal and non-verbal messages that look like audio-visual media, as well as verbal and non-verbal messages that are like the audio media above. Opinion that audio-visual media is a type of media that not only contains sound elements but also contains visible image elements. This is also supported by the opinion of Wati (2016: 44) and Rachmadtullah et al, (2018) that audio visual media is a medium that conveys messages or information by displaying image and sound elements simultaneously. Based on several expert opinions above, audio-visual learning media is able to present material more visually and dynamically, which can increase student involvement and motivation in learning.

The use of this technology makes it possible to convey information through a combination of images, sound and text, so that material can be delivered in a more interesting and easy to understand way. With audio-visual media, concepts about plants and their functions can be explained through videos, animations and simulations, which not only make learning more interesting but also help students relate the material to real-world contexts.

Apart from that, audio-visual learning media allows students to gain experience in more interactive learning activities.

Students can be directly involved in exploring concepts through multimedia activities, which can improve their understanding and skills in natural sciences. This is in line with the characteristics of elementary school age students who are still in the concrete operational stage, where it is easier for them to learn something that can be heard, seen and felt directly.

Conclusion

Based on the results explained above, by improving the learning outcomes of Class IV D students in social studies subjects using audio visual media at SD Negeri 1 Pagaralam, there was an increase in student learning outcomes obtained from tests/evaluations. Initially, only 36.36% of students achieved learning mastery, but after using audio-visual media, this percentage increased to 68.18% in cycle I and 83.36% in cycle II, showing changes and improvements in learning outcomes using audio media visual.

In connection with the results achieved in this research, there are several things that educators should do to improve learning outcomes, especially to activate students in the classroom. In this case, suggestions are given to teaching staff to use creative and innovative media in learning, so that teaching and learning activities become interesting and not monotonous. In this way, the learning you want to convey can get optimal results.

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